

Summary of model predicted changes in lake water chemical parameters assuming scenario SSP5-8.5 where pCO₂ in the atmosphere attains 1100 ppm in 2100. Subscript *i* refers to lake water conditions during the latest sampling (see Table S1), and subscript 1100 represents model results for an atmospheric carbon dioxide concentration of 1100 ppm. Note $\log \Omega_{\text{mineral}} = \log Q/K$, which represents the saturation index for the lake water with respect the aragonite or calcite.

	Lake George	Lake Champlain	Lake Winnepesaukee	Winnisquam Lake	Squam Lake	Ossipee Lake	Newfound Lake	Lake Sunapee	Nubanusit Lake
pH _{<i>i</i>}	7.7	7.83	6.72	6.46	6.56	6.26	6.46	6.3	5.8
pH ₁₁₀₀	6.387	7.576	6.486	6.304	6.354	6.026	6.152	6.073	5.422
Δ pH	1.313	0.254	0.234	0.156	0.206	0.234	0.308	0.227	0.378
Δ log <i>a</i> _{H⁺}	-6.41	-7.93	-6.87	-6.82	-6.78	-6.41	-6.45	-6.46	-5.66
% Change <i>a</i> _{H⁺}	181	56.9	52.6	35.5	46.6	52.6	68.1	51.1	81.9
(log <i>a</i> _{CO₃²⁻}) _{<i>i</i>}	-7.28	-5.621	-7.796	-8.122	-8.044	-8.735	-8.478	-8.635	-10.428
(log <i>a</i> _{CO₃²⁻}) ₁₁₀₀	-8.555	-5.846	-8.0	-8.248	-8.216	-8.933	-8.747	-8.83	-10.407
% Change	180	50.6	46.1	28.9	39.2	44.8	60.1	44.2	-4.8
(log Ω _{aragonite}) _{<i>i</i>}	-2.466	-0.647	-3.485	-3.781	-3.838	-4.531	-4.427	-4.366	-6.565
(log Ω _{aragonite}) ₁₁₀₀	-3.725	-0.853	-3.67	-3.89	-3.988	-4.711	-4.677	-4.542	-6.527
% Change	179	46.5	41.9	25	34.2	40.9	56	40.1	-8.8
(log Ω _{calcite}) _{<i>i</i>}	-2.3	-0.481	-3.319	-3.615	-3.672	-4.365	-4.261	-4.199	-6.399
(log Ω _{calcite}) ₁₁₀₀	-3.56	-0.687	-3.504	-3.725	-3.829	-4.546	-4.511	-4.377	-6.361
% Change	179	46.6	42	25.1	34.3	41	56.1	40.3	-8.7

Summary of model predicted changes in lake water chemical parameters assuming scenario SSP5-8.5 continued

	Dublin Pond	1 st Conn. Lake	2 nd Conn. Lake	Mendums Pond	Mascoma Lake	Sebago Lake	Little Sebago Lake	Rangeley Lake	Moosehead Lake	Mean $\pm$ 1 σ
pH _i	6.48	6.7	6.47	5.42	6.22	7.14	7.22	7.19	7.16	
pH ₁₁₀₀	6.188	6.452	6.29	5.257	6.087	6.749	6.909	6.807	6.806	
Δ pH	0.292	0.248	0.18	0.163	0.133	0.391	0.311	0.383	0.354	0.32 $\pm$ 0.26
$\Delta \log a_{\text{H}^+}$	-6.5	-6.81	-6.76	-5.76	-6.67	-6.98	-7.2	-7.04	-7.06	
% Change a_{H^+}	64.8	55.6	40.9	37.1	30.4	84.4	68.7	82.9	77.3	64.9 $\pm$ 33.6
$(\log a_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}})_i$	-8.42	-7.879	-8.172	-10.952	-8.536	-7.251	-6.948	-7.131	-7.146	
$(\log a_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}})_{1100}$	-8.676	-8.092	-8.324	-10.686	-8.638	-7.615	-7.231	-7.487	-7.472	
% Change	57.3	48	34.6	-59.4	23.4	79.3	62.9	77.7	71.9	49.1 $\pm$ 45.9
$(\log \Omega_{\text{aragonite}})_i$	-4.278	-3584	-3.925	-7.049	-4.113	-3.017	-2.503	-2.802	-2.867	
$(\log \Omega_{\text{aragonite}})_{1100}$	-4.518	-3.779	-4.059	-6.765	-4.199	-3.36	-2.766	-3.137	-3.173	
% Change	53.9	44.1	30.7	-63.2	19.7	75.2	58.7	73.4	67.7	45.3 $\pm$ 46.4
$(\log \Omega_{\text{calcite}})_i$	-4.111	-3.418	-3.759	-6.883	-3.974	-2.852	-2.338	-2.637	-2.702	
$(\log \Omega_{\text{calcite}})_{1100}$	-4.352	-3.613	-3.864	-6.6	-4.033	-3.196	-2.601	-2.972	-3.008	
% Change	54	44.2	30.9	-63.1	19.8	75.3	58.8	73.5	67.8	45.4 $\pm$ 46.4

Summary of model predicted changes in lake water chemical parameters assuming scenario SSP2-4.5 where pCO₂ in the atmosphere attains 600 ppm in 2100. Subscript *i* refers to lake water conditions during the latest sampling, and subscript 600 represents model results for an atmospheric carbon dioxide concentration 600 ppm. Note $\log \Omega_{\text{mineral}} = \log Q/K$, which represents that saturation index for the lake water with respect the aragonite or calcite.

	Lake George	Lake Champlain	Lake Winnepesaukee	Winnisquam Lake	Squam Lake	Ossipee Lake	Newfound Lake	Lake Sunapee	Nubanusit Lake
pH _{<i>i</i>}	7.7	7.83	6.72	6.46	6.56	6.26	6.46	6.3	5.8
pH ₆₀₀	6.873	7.734	6.631	6.405	6.477	6.171	6.33	6.216	5.603
Δ pH	0.827	0.096	0.089	0.055	0.083	0.089	0.13	0.084	0.197
Δ log a _{H⁺}	-6.94	-8.44	-7.36	-7.33	-7.24	-6.9	-6.92	-6.97	-6.04
% Change a _{H⁺}	148	22	20.4	12.6	19.1	20.4	29.7	19.3	44.6
(log a _{CO₃²⁻}) _{<i>i</i>}	-7.28	-5.621	-7.796	-8.122	-8.044	-8.735	-8.478	-8.635	-10.428
(log a _{CO₃²⁻}) ₆₀₀	-8.083	-5.706	-7.873	-8.166	-8.113	-8.811	-8.592	-8.708	-10.417
% Change	146	19.5	17.8	10.1	15.8	17.4	26	16.8	-2.3
(log Ω _{aragonite}) _{<i>i</i>}	-2.466	-0.647	-3.485	-3.781	-3.838	-4.531	-4.427	-4.366	-6.565
(log Ω _{aragonite}) ₆₀₀	-3.26	-0.725	-3.555	-3.819	-3.898	-4.6	-4.533	-4.431	-6.546
% Change	145	17.9	16.1	8.8	13.9	15.9	24.2	15	-4.4
(log Ω _{calcite}) _{<i>i</i>}	-2.3	-0.481	-3.319	-3.615	-3.672	-4.365	-4.261	-4.199	-6.399
(log Ω _{calcite}) ₆₀₀	-3.094	-0.559	-3.39	-3.654	-3.733	-4.435	-4.367	-4.265	-6.38
% Change	145	17.9	16.2	8.9	13.9	15.9	24.3	15.1	-4.3

Summary of model predicted changes in lake water chemical parameters assuming scenario SSP2-4.5 continued

	Dublin Pond	1 st Conn. Lake	2 nd Conn. Lake	Mendums Pond	Mascoma Lake	Sebago Lake	Little Sebago Lake	Rangeley Lake	Moosehead Lake	Mean $\pm$ 1 σ
pH _i	6.48	6.7	6.47	5.42	6.22	7.14	7.22	7.19	7.16	
pH ₆₀₀	6.363	6.601	6.407	5.351	6.175	6.976	7.096	7.029	7.015	
Δ pH	0.117	0.099	0.063	0.069	0.045	0.164	0.124	0.161	0.146	0.147 $\pm$ 0.18
$\Delta \log a_{H^+}$	-6.99	-7.29	-7.28	-6.18	-7.18	-7.48	-7.7	-7.54	-7.56	
% Change a_{H^+}	26.8	22.7	14.5	15.9	10.4	37.6	28.4	36.7	33.1	31.2 $\pm$ 30.6
$(\log a_{CO_3^{2-}})_i$	-8.42	-7.879	-8.172	-10.952	-8.536	-7.251	-6.948	-7.131	-7.146	
$(\log a_{CO_3^{2-}})_{600}$	-8.523	-7.967	-8.225	-10.811	-8.57	-7.403	-7.061	-7.28	-7.279	
% Change	23.5	20	12.2	-32.2	7.8	34.8	25.9	34.1	30.6	23.5 $\pm$ 34.1
$(\log \Omega_{\text{aragonite}})_i$	-4.278	-3.584	-3.925	-7.049	-4.113	-3.017	-2.503	-2.802	-2.867	
$(\log \Omega_{\text{aragonite}})_{600}$	-4.374	-3.663	-3.972	-6.788	-4.142	-3.161	-2.608	-2.943	-2.992	
% Change	22.2	17.9	10.9	-58.4	6.8	32.9	24.1	32.1	28.7	20.5 $\pm$ 36.9
$(\log \Omega_{\text{calcite}})_i$	-4.111	-3.418	-3.759	-6.883	-3.947	-2.852	-2.338	-2.637	-2.701	
$(\log \Omega_{\text{calcite}})_{600}$	-4.208	-3.496	-3.507	-6.622	-3.976	-2.996	-2.443	-2.778	-2.827	
% Change	22.2	18	10.9	-58.4	6.8	32.9	24.1	32.1	28.7	20.6 $\pm$ 36.9

